

TNA Services Management Plan

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Figure 1: TNA Fellow Application Workflow.

Figure 2: TNA Stay Workflow.

List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Meaning
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BoD	Board of Directors
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GA	Grant Agreement
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GenA	General Assembly
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GLAM	Sector that includes Galleries, Libraries, Archives, Museum
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HQ	Head Quarter
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PP	Preparatory Phase
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RI	Research Infrastructure
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TNA	Transnational Access
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WP	Work Package
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WU	Working Unit
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1 Introduction

This deliverable is part of the set of deliverables produced by Work Package 2 that together describe and prepare for the current and future RESILIENCE services. The TNA Management Plan concerns a specific RESILIENCE Service: Transnational Access. Transnational Access is the main part of the Work Unit Research Services within WP 2 for the current phase within RESILIENCE. Accessibility has been flagged by RESILIENCE as a key need of researchers in its (currently still ongoing) user research.¹ According to the Grant Agreement of the RESILIENCE PP it should describe the “[...] criteria of excellence for TNA hosts and users, their rights and duties within the program, quality monitoring procedures and responsibilities (incl. Peer Review Committee), and efficient information providing and research enhancing workflows”.² This will be followed by D2.12 TNA Management Report, which will report on the prototyping and activities conducted by RESILIENCE TNA during the RESILIENCE Preparatory Phase (2022-2026).

1.1 Aim of the TNA Management Plan

Within the Service Strategy, TNA will function as a core service, to be fully coordinated and managed by the future RESILIENCE headquarters.³ The TNA Management Plan thus subscribes to the guiding principles of a RESILIENCE Service, namely that it strives to ensure “[...] expertise, excellence, FAIR, sustainability, transparency, and a clear description of the service[...]”.⁴ It is chiefly informed by three sets of resources: (1) the RESILIENCE TNA programme conducted during the RESILIENCE PP, which provides crucial insight into the current challenges and opportunities (2) research on other transnational programs and activities within the humanities, ESFRI, and other relevant initiatives, to provide background and insight, and (3) the reports and experiences of RelReS (the Research Infrastructure on Religious Studies), which ran a successful fully funded TNA programme from 2018-2021. The latter is important for its comparison with the current in-kind programme, as well as providing the blueprint for the RESILIENCE TNA Programme.

The programme currently operates at a technological readiness level of 6: “A functional version of the product working on a realistic environment able to draw conclusions on the technical and operational capabilities of the product.”⁵ It is in the validating phase of prototyping, where it is functioning in its targeted environment, but is missing a few components that can only be implemented in the next phase, which prevents it from being fully operational.

During the RelReS phase of TNA, 87 users from 23 countries completed their TNA project, spending a total of 180 access weeks. Applicants conducted research within historical religious studies at one of the fourteen available TNA Hosts, at this phase still only consisting of libraries and archives. By July 2021, 19 scholars had published research that been (partially or wholly) produced as a result of a RelReS scholarship in scientific journals, books or as part of dissertations, 49 more were in preparation (in the peer review process or in print), and 10 presentations were given at conferences. Publications in Open Access were collected for the RelReS website until July 2021 and can still be accessed here: <https://reires.eu/online-workshop-materials/publications/>.

¹ Cf. the List of prioritised User Requirements in [RESILIENCE_WP3_D3.5_User-Stories-Catalogue-1st-Batch](#), chap. 4.1, 4.2.

² Grant Agreement-101079792-RESILIENCE PPP, p. 17-18.

³ D2.1 RESILIENCE Service Strategy, p. 20.

⁴ D2.1 RESILIENCE Service Strategy, p 10. For a more thorough outline of these principles, see p. 10-14.

⁵ See <https://horizoneuropencpportal.eu/store/trl-assessment> for an overview of the TRLs and examples.

Given this success and the excellent reputation of the programme, it was decided at the beginning of the RESILIENCE Preparatory Phase to continue running an in-kind, limited version of the programme. It is therefore not a funded programme: the agreements made with TNA Hosts are voluntary and temporary, and do not include any kind of financial or legal obligations; nor do TNA Fellows receive any kind of scholarship unless a TNA Host was able and willing to provide those funds independently. This construction allowed us to profit from the network and experience of ReIReS and thereby ensure that as little expertise and momentum was lost. In doing so we hope to build a tried and tested bridge towards the next phase of the TNA Programme within RESILIENCE.

The Detailed Organization Plan contains a more in-depth list of tasks for T2.6 TNA.⁶ With regard to managing the current version of the TNA programme, the sub-tasks assigned to T2.6 Preparing Trans-National Access services activities should be read iteratively: each year, we prepare TNA activities, analyse the cost and resources available and determine the scope of the programme for that year. This is followed by running the TNA Call and Programme and evaluation and feedback of the programme, both of which together take up most of the effort, as acknowledged by the effort division in the DOP. Each year is concluded by a short internal report, analysing the results, summarising the feedback and evaluation, and making recommendations for the following year. These reports will be used towards the final deliverable, which will allow us to present a truly tested and thriving TNA Service.

This deliverable will therefore outline the TNA Programme from a management perspective as it will be run from June 2026 onward. While it was run as an in-kind service during the PP, this plan assumes funded scholarships within the context of the RESILIENCE Implementation Phase. The remainder of Chapter 1 will describe the current *raison d'être* and describe the main aims of the TNA Programme. Chapter 2 will outline governance and financial management of the programme, while Chapter 3 describes the workflows and procedures related to the TNA Fellows and TNA Hosts. Chapter 4 outlines some key long-term strategies, while Chapter five concludes with a short description on the communication, dissemination, and impact of the future TNA Programme. All the documents related to the TNA Programme cited in the deliverable can be found in the annexes.

1.2 Why a TNA Programme for the Study of Religion?

In its current phase (2022-2026) RESILIENCE is conducting research into the needs of its future users: researchers, scholars, librarians, archivists, and other actors for whom advanced and excellent knowledge of religion is necessary to execute their professional responsibilities. As part of that research WP 3, together with WP2 (led by KU Leuven) and WP4 (led by the Theological University Apeldoorn), designed a two-day "user requirement" workshop aimed at discovering and mapping the needs of future RESILIENCE users.⁷ While the full results of these workshops have yet to be published, interim results have shown the top two factors cited as the most common need amongst researchers were access (chiefly related to accessing academic literature), and networking, with the caveat that both require consistent funding that is often not available in South, Central, and Eastern Europe.⁸

⁶Detailed Organisational Plan, D6.3. See https://www.resilience-ri.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/01/RESILIENCE_WP6_D6.3_-_DetailedOrganisationalPlan-01.00_FINAL.pdf.

⁷Workshop Proceedings – 1st Batch, D3.1 (2024), p. 6-9. See https://www.resilience-ri.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/03/RESILIENCE_WP3_D3.1_WorkshopProceedings1_01.00_FINAL.pdf.

⁸User Stories Catalogue – 1st Batch, D3.5 (2023), p. 18-19. See https://www.resilience-ri.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/11/RESILIENCE_WP3_D3.5_User-Stories-Catalogue-1st-Batch_01.00_FINAL.pdf.

As one of the few truly interdisciplinary academic fields of study, the study of religion both suffers and profits from its vast range of knowledge loci, leading to diverse sets of data, all of which are subject to their own limitations and specifications. They extend across time (historical and contemporary data), context (culture, geography, language, religion), and are multimodal, ranging from texts to numbers to images to physical and material data. The study of religion thus suffers from both an abundance and scarcity of sources, as observed by Lincoln A. Mullen in his article "The Making of America's Public Bible: Computational Text Analysis for Religious History":

"However partial they may be, the archival and the printed record is vast. Despite the labours of librarians and archivists, our sources are inadequately catalogued and indexed. For even the most narrowly targeted scholarly question, the sources available outstrip the historian's time and ability to read."⁹

While it can be expected that digitization could help this issue, the opposite seems to be the case. Digitization exacerbates both the scarcity of undigitized sources and the abundance of digitized sources: the huge number of databases containing digitized collections of primary sources can feel overwhelming to researchers, while at the same time, digitized sources are nowhere near a full representation of the past. However, their accessibility leads researchers "to use those sources rather than other sources which are available in the archive but remain undigitized."¹⁰

In short, it is the combination of digital and physical access to data that is and will remain essential for comprehensive multidisciplinary and multilingual research in the study of religion. Providing only digital data and tools excludes sources as well as specific contents, expressive forms and particular disciplines of the study of religion and does not enable holistic research. Via its Transnational Access Programme, RESILIENCE aims to build this bridge between physical and digital access.

The RESILIENCE TNA Programme offers physical and virtual (as opposed to digital: virtual implies those sources that are only available via onsite computer and/or networking access) across national borders to the most significant tools and sources in those disciplines related to the study of religion. TNA offers support and expertise for research stays at a number of European institutions and libraries that possess unique collections and expertise on the study of religion as a whole. This includes, but is not limited to, the sources and expertise needed to conduct research on the contemporary and historical study of Judaism, Christianity, Buddhism, Islam, new contemporary religious movements, indigenous religions across the globe, and more. Its aim is to facilitate and foster easy access to sources, resources, expertise and services for researchers in The study of religion, while ensuring an efficient access workflow and a single-entry point via the RESILIENCE homepage and central helpdesk.

The TNA service is an answer to the need of scholars to have direct and effective access to sources located in different countries. Often, such collections have not been digitized, and access to these sources is restricted. In order to provide excellence-driven access to its physical resources, TNA partners offer assistance to researchers seeking to conduct a research visit at one of the host facilities offering this

⁹ Lincoln A. Mullen, "The Making of America's Public Bible: Computational Text Analysis for Religious History" In *Digital Humanities and Research Methods in Religious Studies: An Introduction* edited by Christopher D. Cantwell and Kristian Petersen (Berlin, Boston: De Gruyter, 2021), 31-52. <https://doi-org.kuleuven.e-bronnen.be/10.1515/9783110573022-003>.

¹⁰ Lincoln A. Mullen, "The Making of America's Public Bible", 38.

service. The goal of TNA therefore is to facilitate direct and effective access for scholars to the objects of their research: TNA hosts grant access to their collections of manuscripts, rare books, documents and materials, and provide instructions to effectively make use of their collections. This allows scholars to dedicate as much of their research stay to actual research as possible, and allows them to make use of the available local expertise as efficiently as possible.

In addition to access to sources, RESILIENCE also aims to improve the networking capital of its TNA Fellows, by matching TNA scholars with relevant experts who can provide tailored expertise. This offer is unique because it combines access to data of major European research institutions together with access to a vast network of experts for the study of religion. RESILIENCE therefore aims to not only attract academic institutions, but also policy makers, religious institutions, and independent research institutes. In short, the role of the RESILIENCE TNA program is fundamentally a facilitating one, benefiting both host and recipient, and supported by RESILIENCE's excellent professional network.

While many exchange and visiting scholar programmes exist, the specific approach of TNA remains unique. Both the TNA programme conducted in the ReReS and Preparatory Phase projects have shown that unlike for example the Erasmus Programmes it draws early career researchers, starting with PhD candidates, and also including post-doctoral scholars, and early tenure track researchers. Its personalized and tailored approach is also something which the larger EU exchange programmes cannot offer to the same degree. The closest counterpart is the similar set-up of DARIAH's recent launch of [ATRIUM](#), specifically its Transnational Access Scheme Grants – Individual Access for the Digital Humanities. Here there is a similar emphasis on a tailored approach, and a similar audience. The key difference is that ATRIUM TNA Hosts focus on the Digital Humanities, whereas RESILIENCE leverages its expertise on the study of religion across all disciplines. The similar set-up could allow for a future collaboration between the two programmes.

1.3 RESILIENCE TNA Programme 2022-2024

During the PP, RESILIENCE TNA ran a limited TNA Programme. While the D2.12 TNA Management Report will analyse and report on the full results of that programme, it is worthwhile to highlight a few key insights and recommendations on the current status quo. In October 2023 an evaluation was held of the first year, which resulted in a confidential Strategy Report for 2023-2026, as well as a number of key recommendations.

The key difference in the two versions of the programme is that the prototyping programme was an unfunded, fully in-kind programme, whereas we expect the future RESILIENCE TNA Programme to be funded. Management of the TNA Host Network is work of WP2 with KU Leuven as lead. WP2 contains four main work units: Data (responsible for the data management within the current consortium and future RI), Training (responsible for developing a training programme), and IT (responsible for outlining IT Services and support for the future RI), one of which is Transnational Access. A total of 798 effort days were dedicated to prototyping the future TNA Programme, divided amongst the consortium partners. 52% of that effort is divided amongst KU Leuven and INFAL. All partners received 30 effort days for the TNA task, which are being used to run a prototype of the TNA programme.

Currently RESILIENCE TNA has signed an agreement until 2026 with of 17 hosts: FSCIRE (Bologna, IT), KU Leuven (BE), Sofia University "St. Kliment Ohridski"(BG), Theological University of Apeldoorn (NL),

University of Münster (DE), University of Sarajevo (BIH), Volos Academy for Theological Studies (GR), Bar-Ilan University (Ramat Gan, IL), Bektashi World Center (Tirana, AL), CIRCSE (Milan, IT), mikado Library (Aachen, DE), New Georgian University (Poti, GE), University of Ljubljana, Faculty of Theology (SI), J.A. Comenius Museum (Uherský Brod, CZ), "Saint Epiphanius" Cultural Academy (CY), Archivio Generale Arcivescovile di Bologna, AAB (Bologna, IT), and the University of Warsaw (PL).

RESILIENCE TNA has also signed an agreement until October 2025 with the five Italian hosts that are part of the ITSERR consortium (Italian Strengthening of the ESFRI RI RESILIENCE project, funded by NextGenerationEU): Institute of Information Science and Technologies "Alessandro Faedo" (ISTI-CNR) in Pisa, affiliated to the National Research Council (CNR), Università di Modena e Reggio Emilia (UniMORE), Università di Napoli "l'Orientale" (UniOr), Università degli Studi di Palermo (UniPa), Università di Torino (UniTo).

Given that there were not financial or legal obligations, the agreement between RESILIENCE TNA and the TNA Host were framed in the context of a Memorandum of Understanding (see annex 1 for the template). The MOU lists the mandatory in-kind services as determined by RESILIENCE TNA, which are: free access to collections, provide a workplace, aid in navigating collections, and arranging a meet up with at least one on-site expert. Additional in-kind services offered voluntarily by hosts included paid or reduced accommodation, public transportation discounts, airport transfers, hospitality services, access to digital services, free printing, scanning, and copying.

As of 1 October 2024, RESILIENCE TNA has received 57 TNA Fellow Applications, 46 of which were accepted (this includes applications for 2024-2025). Of those, a total of 29 research stays have already been completed, and 10 will still be completed in the upcoming academic year (this includes two fellows who postponed their research stay). Six TNA Fellows had to postpone or cancel their research stay: four cited geopolitical tensions in Israel-Gaza, and two a lack of funding.

The current version of RESILIENCE TNA requires three roles (these can be fulfilled by the same person). They are: programme officer, operational officer, and communications officer. Within the PP the Programme Officer role was fulfilled by the WU Research Services Lead KU Leuven (118 effort days), while the Operational Officer was fulfilled by WU Research Services Team Member INFAl (300 effort days). Communications was conducted by both INFAl and the WP CDE Team Lead TUA (60 effort days).

Very few aspects of these roles were automatized, leading to a relatively high personnel investment. Therefore, in May 2024 planning began for a RESILIENCE TNA Portal: an online platform for both TNA Hosts and TNA Fellows that would be embedded within the RESILIENCE RI. Not only will this provide a more efficient overview of the available hosts and resources, it will also partially automate the application and evaluation processes within the programme.

1.4 Key Recommendations of the Year One (2023) Review

The year one review led to a number of observations and recommendations; positive trends that should be taken onboard for the next RESILIENCE phase were twofold. First, the results of Midterm evaluation results of the TNA Programme were very positive. Key features that were appreciated the most by Fellows that should be maintained were: (1) The emphasis on personal contact and practical help in preparing the visit; (2) The networking opportunities, especially the chance to meet up with a local expert; (3) The chance

to share research with local researchers. Secondly, the geographic diversity of the programme, both in terms of TNA Hosts and TNA Fellows, was quite astounding. In the first two years fifteen countries were represented amongst the successful TNA Applicants. This diversity should be maintained and encouraged as much as possible.

In addition to these trends, two key areas of growth were identified, leading to two recommendations. The first concerns the **automatization of workflows** to reduce personnel costs and increase efficiency and ease of access to the programme. Any exchange programme requires a lot of human effort, but there are ways to increase the efficiency of specific workflows and procedures. The recommendation therefore is to develop a dedicated platform on the RESILIENCE marketplace, to be used by RESILIENCE members, TNA Hosts, and TNA Fellows. While there is no effort for prototyping or developing such a TNA portal, it should form an integral part of the future TNA Management Plan. The second focuses on the controlled **expansion of the TNA Hosting Network** to increase the quality and diversity of the hosts for TNA Fellows. The WU Research Service recommended a focus on the following areas: religious diversity, expansion in Eastern Europe (aligning with WP₄), Southwestern Europe and Northern Europe, and to explore expansion into the UK, the US, and MENA. MENA is currently not an option due to the regional instability, but should be included in the long-term strategy.

In the two chapters that follow, the above recommendations, as well as previous experiences with TNA will inform this first outline of the TNA Programme, describing governance and financial management, the required procedures and workflows on the management of TNA Fellows and Hosts, and the initial plans for a TNA Portal to facilitate these.

2. Governance and Financial Management of the TNA Programme

Within the current RESILIENCE timeline, the TNA Programme will be managed under the auspices of WP₂ Services as a prototype programme until May 2026, which is when the PP phase will end. From June 2026 onward RESILIENCE aims to transition into its implementation phase, and with the official RESILIENCE TNA programme will be launched. The current intention is that TNA Programme will then begin to transition from its current in-kind programme to a funded fellowship programme. From 2030 RESILIENCE foresees funds for hiring a fulltime software developer, which means that from that moment on we can focus on the development of the TNA Portal. It should be noted that this timeline is dependent on how RESILIENCE will evolve in the next two year. The TNA Programme outlined below should therefore be viewed as a living document that will be updated and adapted for the remainder of the PP phase.

2.1 Governance: Roles and Responsibilities

In the next phase RESILIENCE aims to become a distributed research infrastructure, with national nodes contributing to the RESILIENCE ERIC. Most of the programme's activities will be managed within the national nodes, with the exception of a few key financial, legal, and governance responsibilities that, within the current plan, will likely need to be managed at the EU level. Each national node provides a National Host Officer, and each TNA Host also provides a TNA Coordinator and, if possible, a TNA Contact Person. Finally, the TNA Programme requires a Peer Review Board, which consists of a mix of RESILIENCE and TNA staff. It should be noted that the division between HQ and national node responsibilities outlined

below cannot be finalized at this stage of the project, and should therefore not be viewed as definitive. The account below bases itself on input from the PP TNA Programme and the Financial Sustainability Plan.¹¹

2.1.1 HQ TNA Management Team

HQ staff will contribute to those aspects of the programme that cannot be run at the national level. However, the current HQ staff does not foresee a specific TNA Officer. As such, these responsibilities will be divided according to expertise amongst the current roles foreseen at HQ, including the Communications Officer, Legal and Administration Office, and where necessary the Open Science and Technology Transfer Officer. Key duties concerning the TNA Programme at HQ include the following:

1. Legal and financial management of the TNA Grants
2. Legal and financial management of the TNA Hosting Network
3. Coordinating the Peer Review Board
4. TNA Communication and Dissemination at the EU level
5. Evaluation and monitoring of the programme
6. Maintaining the TNA Portal

The current plan presupposes a steady growth of the TNA Programme, both in terms of TNA Fellows and TNA Hosts. However, we expect that the TNA Portal will offset the required increase in effort so that the personnel hours for TNA can remain steady.

2.1.2 TNA National Nodes

National nodes are the national members of the RESILIENCE community. Each national node has a TNA National Host Officer, who coordinates all the TNA Hosts for their country.¹² In accordance with the Service Strategy, the National Host Officer will be responsible (within the limits of the TNA Programme) for:

1. Grow and maintain the national TNA Network
2. Managing all national TNA activities
3. Community outreach and engagement activities
4. Monitoring and evaluation of the programme at the national level
 - a. Define local Key Performance Indicators (KPI) and collect data for monitoring.
 - b. Develop local policies (access policy, data policy ...) and monitor their impact in line with the RESILIENCE RI policies.¹³

At the TNA Host institutions themselves, two personnel roles have been identified, though these can be filled by one person. These are the TNA Coordinator and the TNA Contact Person. Their key responsibilities are outlined below:

¹¹ See D1.3 Financial Sustainability Plan, https://www.resilience-ri.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/08/RESILIENCE_WP1_D1.3_FSP_FinancialSustainabilityPlan_01.00_FINAL.pdf.

¹² Financial Sustainability Plan, p. 19.

¹³ D2.1 Service Strategy, https://www.resilience-ri.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/04/RESILIENCE_WP2_D2.1_Services-Preparation-and-Implementation-Strategy_01.00_FINAL.pdf.

TNA Coordinator	TNA Contact Person
Reviews applications	Point of contact for TNA Scholar
Provides a letter of invitation	Responsible for practical and administrative duties
Ensures a smooth operation within university bureaucracy	Keeps RESILIENCE TNA Coordinator informed of progress

Of these, the TNA Coordinator is mandatory. They ensure physical and administrative access to the institute, and form the main point of contact for the National Host Officer. They should therefore have a senior position in the faculty or institute. In practice it has been shown that researchers at this level rarely have the time for resources for the practical work required to prepare a TNA Visit, which is then often outsourced to junior researchers. By creating an official role for the latter, we hope to better recognize the work often done by junior researchers, as well as outline the extent (i.e. limits) of their role. Nevertheless, experience has shown that smaller TNA Hosts (especially independent libraries and archives) do not have the personnel for two roles, and will likely conflate the two roles.

2.1.3 Peer Review Board

The Peer Review Board has a twofold role: evaluation TNA Host applications and evaluation TNA Fellow applications. The board forms a continuation of the TNA Host Evaluation Board created for preparation phase, and will consist of seven members:

1. RESILIENCE HQ CDE Representative
2. RESILIENCE HQ M Representative
3. RESILIENCE Advisory Board Member
4. Two active TNA Host Coordinator(s) who are not included in the list above. These members should, where possible, represent a geographic region not included by the members above. They will rotate every two years, and are invited to join by the Access Programme Coordinator .
5. Two R3/R4 researchers on the study of religion¹⁴: one representing disciplines within the Humanities, and one representing disciplines within the Social Sciences. These members should, where possible, represent a geographic region not included by the members above. They will rotate every two years.

Criteria have been developed for both the TNA Host applications and the TNA Fellow applications (see section 3.1.2 and 3.2.1). The Peer Review Board is responsible for reviewing both sets of applications, and should be prepared to provide feedback on its decisions where required. Contesting the decision of the board is not viewed as necessary for TNA Fellows, as they can incorporate the feedback and apply again at a later stage. A contesting procedure should be in place for the potential TNA Hosts.¹⁵

¹⁴ The EU has identified four unique EU Researcher Career profiles to describe career level. These are categorized according to the level of research independence and influence in the field, with R1 equivalent to a PhD candidate, and R4 equivalent to an international leading scholar in the field. See <https://www.more-4.eu/indicator-tool/career-stages-r1-to-r4>.

¹⁵ This is still under development.

2.2 Financial Management of the TNA Programme

Given that the current phase of the programme is unfunded, this section describes a future version of the TNA Programme and should still be viewed as in development. The financial plan below is primarily based on the [D1.3 Financial Sustainability Plan](#).¹⁶ Costs for running a fully implemented TNA Programme can be divided into four categories:

1. TNA Grant Management
2. Personnel and Management costs at RESILIENCE HQ and National Nodes.
3. In-kind contributions provided by the TNA Host, including but not limited to: access to physical and digital TNA Host Infrastructures, meetings with onsite experts, meeting up with experts, workplace, and access to (future) RESILIENCE services and networking events.
4. Internal service: operational costs.

2.2.1 TNA Fellow Grants

The TNA Fellow grants will be managed by the RESILIENCE TNA HQ. The Financial Sustainability Plan includes an initial estimate of TNA Grants for the Implementation phase. For TNA mobility grants for individuals, 20k is foreseen for 20 TNA Fellows per annum. For the TNA mobility grants for teams a total of 70k is foreseen per annum, estimated at 5k for each team member, for teams of 3 members, for a duration of about 1 month – as estimated by the ITSERR project, which is testing this specific type of TNA.¹⁷

The TNA individual mobility will operate on the principle of: as flexible as possible, as rigid as necessary. What this means in practice is that we do not mandate specific accommodation or flights, nor how much is spent on travel or accommodation. The exception to this is if the TNA host offers in-kind accommodation or has an institutional agreement with a third-party on accommodation – in this case the TNA Fellow will be obligated to use this.

Each TNA Fellow will receive the national equivalent of 2000 euros for their TNA stay, with a minimum of five working days, and a maximum of two working weeks. The grant should at minimum cover affordable travel costs, accommodation, (some) living expenses, and (where needed) access to the institution's collections. TNA Fellows will be encouraged to travel as sustainably as possible, with flights discouraged if the train and/or bus alternative takes eight hours or less. Accommodation can be booked independently by the TNA Fellow, unless the TNA Host has an existing third-party or internal accommodation for visiting scholars.

TNA Fellows will sign an agreement with RESILIENCE TNA outlining the grant package and the main duties the TNA Fellow should subscribe to.¹⁸ The following requirements need to have been met:

1. They have been accepted into the RESILIENCE TNA Programme
2. They have completed the TNA Visit Form. This form lists their personal details, including account number, the aims of their visit, the specific material(s) they would like to access, the expert(s) they

¹⁶ D1.3 Financial Sustainability Plan p. 17.

¹⁷ See <https://www.itserr.it/index.php/itserr-tna/> for more information.

¹⁸ In the PP phase of the project such an agreement was not necessary, as neither the TNA Fellow nor the TNA Host incurred financial or legal obligations. A template for such an agreement will be included in the final version of this deliverable.

- would like to meet, the finalized dates of their visit, proof of bookings, and a budget of expected expenses.
3. The TNA Fellow form is signed by both the TNA Fellow and the THA Host Coordinator, and has been forwarded to RESILIENCE TNA.
 4. They are aware that they need to make their insurance arrangements for the full duration of their research stay.

RESILIENCE TNA transfers the money to the TNA Fellow at the beginning of the month of the planned visit, who can then proceed with their travel arrangements. In this way we hope to increase the flexibility of the TNA Fellow, who can, for example, choose to spend the grant on cheaper accommodation for a longer stay, or choose a cheaper method of travel to upgrade their accommodation.

2.2.2 Personnel and Management Costs

The exact financial management of the TNA Programme is still in development. However, the table below gives an indication of the main tasks and personnel costs of managing RESILIENCE TNA in the implementation phase. Personnel costs are divided between RESILIENCE TNA HQ and RESILIENCE TNA National Node. RESILIENCE HQ is responsible for all EU-level tasks of the programme, mainly concerning the financial and legal management of the programme, and monitoring and reporting. Most of the TNA activities will be carried out at the national level, which will be managed by the National Host Officer at each national node. Each national node will have a TNA National Host Officer who will manage the national network of TNA Hosts and Fellows.

TNA Personnel		
	Tasks	FTE
RESILIENCE HQ	Initial stages of onboarding new TNA Hosts	0,3 FTE ¹⁹
	Maintaining contact with TNA Hosts	
	Grant administration	
	Monitoring and reporting at RESILIENCE-EU level	
	Updating/maintaining TNA Portal	
	Managing TNA Calls for Applications	
RESILIENCE National Nodes		
National Host Officer	Build and grow the local TNA Network	0,1 FTE per member
	Service Contribution	
	Outreach and engagement	
	Monitoring and evaluation	
	Point of Contact for TNA Fellows	
TNA HOST Partners		

¹⁹ This effort is an estimation based on current experience. It should be clarified at later stages if the HQ will have the financial capability for sustaining it or whether this effort should be distributed.

TNA Host Coordinator	Maintaining contact with RESILIENCE	4 hrs per month
	Sharing all TNA Communication Updates	
	PR/Networking	
	Membership TNA Peer Review Board	
TNA Contact Person	Contact with TNA Fellow	20 hrs per TNA Fellow
	Preparing Visit	
	Running the visit	
	Evaluation visit	

2.2.3 Operational Costs

No operational costs beyond the TNA grants and personnel are foreseen for until the TNA Portal is implemented. Until that time, TNA software maintenance is part of the overall RESILIENCE online maintenance. Software maintenance for RESILIENCE has been planned at three resources for 0,5FTE in 2026-2027, 1FTE in 2028-2031.²⁰ This is intended for the maintenance of ITSERR/RESILIENCE-born tools.

3. Management of TNA Fellows and TNA Hosts

During the PP phase a number of workflows and procedures were developed for the management of both TNA Fellows and TNA Hosts. These are still in the process of being tested, evaluated and fine-tuned. This chapter describes the operational management of both fellows and hosts, which will primarily take place the level of the national nodes.

3.1 Management of TNA Fellows

TNA Fellows are expected to conduct original research that results in scientific output, to be published in open access where possible. This includes academic articles, monographs, books and book chapters, conference presentations, science communication, and research data sets. They will meet up with an expert in their topic or field: this meeting should be a minimum of one hour and should focus on the specific research questions of the TNA Fellow. In addition to this, the TNA Fellow should, if possible and desirable, have the opportunity to present their research to onsite peers, via a seminar, or staff meeting, or other format. In short, the TNA Fellow experience is a personalized one, tailored to their specific research and networking needs. The experience in both ReIReS and the RESILIENCE PP has shown that the programme attracts junior and intermediate scholars, ranging from the doctoral level to the equivalent of assistant and associate professors.

Two different types of TNA grants are foreseen for the implementation phase: individual mobility grants and team mobility grants. The individual mobility grants have been tested during both the ReIReS and RESILIENCE PP phase; during both phases the interest in the programme was consistent, diverse, and surprisingly popular, especially given the lack of funding during the PP phase. Physical access to sources is clearly still not only necessary and fundamental for researchers studying religion, it is also not sufficiently available or easy to access. This is also not likely to change within the field, given the immense cost and

²⁰ Financial Sustainability Plan, p. 20.

effort associated with digitizing collections, and effort that is simply not possible for the small institutions contributing to the study of religion.

The team mobility grants are still being developed and tested by ITSERR, the Italian project in support of RESILIENCE. At this stage of the project not enough insight and information is available on management of these fellowships to include in this beta deliverable. This will be included in the final version of the deliverable. To that end, in what follows an initial overview of the workflows and procedures for the individual mobility grants will be described.

3.1.1 TNA Fellow Application Workflow

In the current phase, TNA Fellows apply during the Call for Applications via the RESILIENCE TNA website using an online application form.²¹ Once the call closes, the applications are sent to the respective hosts. Each TNA Host fills in the TNA Fellow Evaluation Chart for each applicant, and sends this back with their decision. RESILIENCE TNA then emails all the candidates individually with the final decisions, putting the TNA Coordinators of their future TNA Hosts in CC.

With the implementation of a funded TNA programme as well as the TNA Portal, the application process will have to change. Potential TNA Fellows will apply via the TNA Portal using the application form. All the application forms are collected every two months and sent to their respective TNA Hosts. Each TNA Host fills in the TNA Fellow Evaluation Chart (see Annex 7.8) and sends this back to the TNA National Host Coordinator with a recommendation report. The TNA National Host Coordinator collects all the recommendation reports and sends them to the TNA Host Evaluation Board Committee, who have one month to make a decision. These are communicated by completing the recommendation reports and sending them back to the TNA National Host Coordinator. While this can be done in a live meeting, it is also possible for each board member to issue his/her vote via email to the programme officer. In this way, prospective TNA Fellows should hear their results within three months of applying. See the figure below for an overview of this process.

²¹ See <https://www.resilience-ri.eu/resilience-tna-application-form/> for the current version of the application form. See Annex 7.11 if the application is currently closed.

Figure 1: TNA Fellow Application Workflow.

3.1.2 Criteria of excellence

The following criteria were developed for TNA Fellow Applications and are available on the current RESILIENCE TNA [website](#). A candidate must obtain a minimum of 50% of the points given for the five main selection and ranking criteria. The yes or no questions function as an extra criterion that can be used to when weighing equal criteria candidates.

Main selection and ranking criteria²²

1. Research quality of the proposal **(0–15 points)**
2. Career profile of the potential user **(0–10 points)**
3. Potential of the research project **(0–10 points)**
4. Match between expertise/collections TNA Host and research project **(0-10 points)**
5. The project has European relevance **(0–5 points)**

Extra criteria²³

1. Equal opportunity: the project is led by, or includes, a female group leader or principle investigator or team member; OR the gender balance within the group members is fulfilled (40/60); OR it includes a specific focus on gender issues **(yes/no)**
2. Equal opportunity: The project is led by, or benefits, or includes, a differently abled group leader or principal investigator or team member OR it includes a specific focus on disability/trauma issues. **(yes/no)**
3. The TNA scholar can be considered an early career scholar (Master, PhD, post-doc) **(yes/no)**
4. The project is proposed by a scholar who has not received a RESILIENCE TNA scholarship before **(yes/no)**
5. The project requires a strong integration between access to physical collections and the use of digital tools **(yes/no)**

3.1.3 TNA Fellow Rights and duties

Upon acceptance into the programme, TNA Fellows have the following rights and duties.

Rights:

1. They receive a grant to contribute to the costs of their research stay;
2. They will receive free access to the collections of the TNA Host Institution of their choice;
3. They will meet a minimum of one expert related to the topic of their research;
4. They can present their research at the TNA Host Institution of their choice;
5. They will receive (if desired) a TNA certificate of their stay;²⁴
6. RESILIENCE Membership (length and benefits to be determined), access to services and training.

Duties

1. Communicate their preferences with their prospective TNA Host: research materials, experts, preferred dates, and practical requirements regarding travel and accommodation;

²² A rubric to help TNA Hosts select their candidates is still in development.

²³ Cf. the UN [Sustainable Development Goals](#) 10 (Reduced Inequality), 5 (Gender Equality), and 4 (Quality Education).

²⁴ See Annex 7.7 for the current TNA Certificate Template.

2. Conduct and conclude their research **in person** at the TNA Host of their choice. Excluding unusual circumstances such COVID-19, exclusively remote or virtual TNA visits are not in principle part of the TNA Fellowships;
3. They have met up with the TNA Coordinator or TNA Person at least once during their visit;
4. Present their research at the TNA Host of their institution;
5. Complete the TNA Fellow Report upon the completion of their stay, including: a short summary of the conducted research (mandatory), the RESILIENCE TNA evaluation form (mandatory), pictures or video material of their stay for RESILIENCE social media channels (optional).
6. Inform RESILIENCE TNA once the results of the research have been published.

3.1.4 TNA Fellow Quality monitoring: procedures and responsibilities

Quality monitoring for TNA Fellows is conducted in a number of different ways.

1. **Evaluating the TNA visits.** This will be done in two ways: (1) Evaluation form and annual report of the results (cf. Annex 7.5 for the current version of the evaluation); (2) Occasional visits at TNA Hosts during a TNA visit by the national node coordinator.
2. **Terms and Conditions:** TNA Fellows are subject to the programme Terms and Conditions.²⁵
3. **Impact measurement and analysis.**²⁶

3.2 Management of RESILIENCE TNA Hosts

Management of the TNA Hosts can be divided into two main categories: maintaining the TNA Hosting Network (all the duties surrounding hosting TNA Fellows) and growing the TNA Hosting Network. It is important to note that institutes will not need to be part of a national RESILIENCE consortium to become a TNA Host. As TNA Hosts, institutes join the national hosting network, whose point of contact will be the TNA national node coordinator. For the most up to date list of qualifying countries, we follow Horizon Europe Recommendations during the PP.

At the start of the PP onboarding new TNA Hosts was an active process where RESILIENCE pursued negotiations with potential new hosts. A passive process was set up as well, where interested institutions could contact RESILIENCE for more information. This passive process was adopted within year 1 of the PP, and should be maintained during the implementation phase. In the long-term, candidate institutions will apply for RESILIENCE TNA via the TNA Portal.

3.2.1 Criteria of excellence

The following formal criteria were developed for all TNA Host interested in joining the TNA Hosting Network. The aim of these criteria is to ensure the excellence, quality, and hospitality of the potential TNA Host via a transparent process.

1. Aware of the full commitment required to fulfil minimum duties of a TNA host (yes/no)
2. Dean/Director of the institution has signed the memorandum of understanding (yes/no)
3. Has appointed a TNA Coordinator and TNA Contact Person (can be one person) (yes/no)

²⁵ See https://docs.google.com/document/d/1RLqfYXdmwYA-Mh_yormFxpzWJNBeV5fvd7grSRMTf4s/edit?tab=t.o for the current version.

²⁶ The RESILIENCE TNA impact assessment methodology is currently being developed in cooperation with WP5 and will be presented by WP5 in: RESILIENCE D5.1 Impact Analysis.

4. Holds one or more academic collections relevant to the study of religion (yes/no)
5. Host institution has a number of in-house experts/senior scholars affiliated with disciplines related to the study of religion and/or experts on the collections in their holdings (yes/no)
6. Host institution is located within Horizon Europe list of European nations²⁷ (yes/no)
7. Host institution is GDPR (General Data Protection Regulation) compliant and inasmuch as possible operates according to OA and FAIR principles (compliance with GED is encouraged but not mandatory) (yes/no)
8. Host institution has an online presence (newsletters, social media, website) which can be utilized for RESILIENCE communication and PR (yes/no)
9. Host institution intends to provide a safe space to excellent researchers regardless of gender, age, religion, nationality or impairments (yes/no).

These criteria can largely be maintained for the next phase of the TNA Programme, with this exception that the next phase will likely require some legal and financial criteria to be included as well.

3.2.2 Rights and duties

Each TNA Host signs a grant agreement with RESILIENCE outlining the duties and responsibilities of each partner. In the current phase the rights and duties of both the TNA Host and RESILIENCE TNA have been outlined in a Memorandum of Understanding (see Annex 7.1 for template). This version does not include any financial or legal obligations. For the funded version of the programme, a new agreement is still in development – it will depend, among other things, on the future legal structure of RESILIENCE, the relationship between national nodes and RESILIENCE HQ, and the type of institution applying to become TNA Host. While the list below captures the main framework of the agreement between RESILIENCE and the TNA Host, it should still be viewed as in development.

The TNA Host commits to:

1. Appoint a RESILIENCE TNA coordinator and a TNA Contact Person for the duration of the MOU. These roles may be performed by one person, if preferred.
2. Agree to a minimum number of TNA recipients per academic year.
3. Review and accept TNA applications for your institution, using the TNA Review Criteria.
4. Ensure free and easy access to its collections
5. Ensure the provision of a comfortable workspace for each TNA recipient
6. Match TNA recipients with at minimum one onsite scholar or expert.
7. Report to RESILIENCE on the performance of the TNA program and help to develop and improve the TNA program and its procedures.
8. Participate in promoting RESILIENCE TNA, TNA Scholars, and TNA research results, through internal and external communication channels.
9. Permit RESILIENCE to publish a description of your physical and digital collections on your TNA Host webpage as a part of the RESILIENCE website.

²⁷ For the most up to date list of qualifying countries, please see: https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/news/all-research-and-innovation-news/updates-association-third-countries-horizon-europe-2021-12-21_en

RESILIENCE TNA commits to:

1. RESILIENCE offers access to the RESILIENCE PR and communication channels for recognition and dissemination of the TNA HOST unique collections
2. RESILIENCE offers access to a top-level network of researchers and institutions related to the study of religion.
3. RESILIENCE offers access to a growing set of services and tools tailored to research within your fields of expertise.
4. RESILIENCE is responsible for grant management, and organising and disseminating each TNA Call for Fellowships.
5. RESILIENCE undertakes to grow the TNA Host network.
6. RESILIENCE monitors the quality of the TNA programme as a whole via targeted evaluation processes.
7. RESILIENCE is responsible for keeping all TNA Hosts up to date on all relevant news and updates concerning the programme and the life of the RI in general.

3.3.3 TNA Host Application Workflow

During the PP a detailed application workflow was developed which has proven itself over the past two years. While still requiring some fine-tuning, especially if the TNA Hosting Network scales up exponentially, experience has shown that the emphasis on personal contact demonstrated below is crucial for the success of subsequent TNA Fellow visits.

Step 1: An institute contacts RESILIENCE TNA via the TNA Portal, providing basic details and motivation.

Step 2: The TNA Management Team conducts a short investigation and decides whether to proceed. If yes, they create an account for the prospective host, which will include the following information and documentation:

1. Template of the Memorandum of Understanding.²⁸
2. Criteria of Excellence (see above).
3. A short questionnaire to gain insight into the exact expertise and collections on offer.²⁹
4. Link to the other TNA Host webpages from the TNA Portal.

Once the TNA Host fills in the questionnaire online, the TNA Management Team sets up a meeting with the new host to discuss key rights and duties, outline the grant management process, discuss the available collections and archives, and ensures that the TNA Host fully understands everything that is required. A number of guides and tips were collected in the PP phase to aid this part of the process, which will be collected into a single guide for the next phase.³⁰ The following commitments should be clarified:

1. Rundown of Admissions Criteria, MOU, and rights/duties of a TNA Host
2. Appointing a TNA Coordinator/Contact Person

²⁸ See Annex 7.1 for the template currently in use.

²⁹ [See here for the extensive version](#). This has been used for the first two years of the PP, but was deemed too long and unwieldy in practice. An updated version is still in development.

³⁰ See <https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1BCNbAM86glxcDgYqymirFv3XmoAxgWaP> for the current guide, email templates, meeting checklists, and more.

3. Providing a workspace, access to collections, and all the requested materials
4. Commitment towards introducing TNA scholars to onsite expert(s).
5. Timeline: application process, deadlines, call for TNA Scholars.

It is especially important to highlight the appointment criteria for the TNA Host Coordinator and the legal requirements and time frame needed to sign the agreement. Experience has shown that given that this often requires a high-level faculty or institute member, the process can take some time. To conclude this step, the TNA Programme Coordinator writes a short recommendation report for the Peer Review Board.³¹

Step 3: The TNA Peer Review Board meets every six months to discuss the TNA Host applications received.³² This can also be done a-synchronously via email. These applications are summarized and prepared by the TNA Programme Coordinator. Each board member makes an individual decision according to the information included in the report. This decision is added to the report by the TNA Programme Coordinator, who communicates it to the respective candidate TNA Hosts. Board members are obliged to vote: three votes suffices for a positive advice. In case the board cannot come to a decision, the application is forward to the RESILIENCE Board of Directors, who have the final vote. Each TNA Host is then confirmed by the GenA.

Step 4: The TNA Host is informed of the results. They will in turn inform TNA Management within a certain time frame whether they wish to accept and move forward with the process or not. Once both parties have agreed, the agreement is made up and signed. All the agreements are collected before every meeting of the RESILIENCE General Assembly, who finally confirms the acceptance of the new TNA Host(s).

3.2.4 TNA Host Onboarding Workflow

The first step for onboarding a new TNA Host is the appointment of the TNA Coordinator and/or TNA Contact Person. They will also form the point of contact for RESILIENCE TNA, and are responsible for delivering and checking the information needed to create a TNA Host profile in the TNA Portal. This information can already be gathered before the GenA greenlights the decision, but cannot be published. Once the profile is completed to the satisfaction of both parties, it will be published, at which point the TNA Host can begin to participate in the programme.

Currently each TNA Host has their own webpage on the [RESILIENCE TNA website](#), showcasing their key resources and expertise. This includes both physical and virtual resources. In general, virtual sources and services available onsite at the TNA Host. In some cases, once a fellow has been accepted TNA Hosts can add to this benefit in the shape of access to digital collections and services. The TNA Portal will take over this role in the future version of the programme.

3.2.5 TNA Visit Workflow

One month after the application deadline, the TNA hosts and the TNA Evaluation Board have decided which applicants are accepted and which are rejected, and the TNA Programme Coordinator informs the applicants. Then the local TNA contact person begins to make the arrangements for the research stay with

³¹ See Annex 7.3 for the current template of this report.

³² This length of time is subject further insight, as currently it is not clear how often TNA Host applications will be received in the next RESILIENCE Phase.

the TNA fellow. The figure below outlines the process with the inclusion of the portal; see annex 7.2 for the workflow currently in use and distributed to TNA Hosts.

1. First Contact	TNA Fellow	Ask for dates, resources, experts; clarify conditions	TNA Host Contact		
2. ASAP	TNA Fellow	Agree on dates, resources, experts, conditions	TNA Host Contact	Ensure resources are available at agreed dates	TNA Host (Library/Collection/University/Facility)
3. At least 2 weeks before TNA stay			TNA Host Contact	Arrange library card/access passes	TNA Host (Library/Collection/University/Facility)
	TNA Fellow	Inform about arrangements, clarify organisational matters	TNA Host Contact	Arrange meeting(s), participation in acad. activities	Local Expert(s)/Research Group(s)
4. At least 1 week before TNA stay			TNA Host Contact	Prepare research needs: resources, office, etc.	TNA Host (Library/Collection/University/Facility)
5. During the TNA stay	TNA Fellow	Arrange Meet and Greet; contact/support	TNA Host Contact	Scientific support	Local Expert(s)/Research Group(s)
6. One week after TNA stay	TNA Fellow	Request for Evaluation	TNA Portal		
7. ASAP			TNA Programme Coordinator	Feedback and discussion on results of evaluation	TNA Host Contact and Coordinator

Figure 2: TNA Stay Workflow.

3.2.6 Quality monitoring: procedures and responsibilities

Quality monitoring for TNA Hosts is conducted in a number of different ways.

1. **Biannual TNA Host Trainings.** These were created and trialed in the PP phase for new hosts to create a uniform sense of experience and quality. They outline the workflow, key responsibilities, and include testimonies and experiences from TNA Fellows. Currently these are still confidential.
2. **Evaluation form and annual report.** Each TNA Host will be asked to fill in an evaluation form annually.³³ The TNA Management Team compiles and analyses the results, and reports on the status quo, as well as possible recommendations.
3. **Impact measurement and analysis.**³⁴

4. Long-Term Strategies of the TNA Programme

The previous chapters described the key aspects of running and maintaining the TNA Programme during the RESILIENCE implementation phase. This chapter outlines the long-term plans that have been developed as a result of the PP phase, which should be taken into account for the next phase of the programme.

4.1 TNA Portal

Multiple references have been made to the TNA Portal. The ultimate aim of the TNA programme is to provide fast, efficient access to collections and experts via an ongoing call, where RESILIENCE functions as a facilitator rather than organizer. The portal is not yet in development: the need for it became clear during the first two years of the PP. In that phase, TNA Calls for Proposals were run on an occasional basis: two annual calls, and four bi-annual calls. The switch towards the latter took place in 2024, halfway the prototyping phase, to shift the calls away from the summer period, allowing scholars to apply for summer research stays – a period which was not possible to apply for with the timing of the previous two calls. However, two calls per year is still not a very flexible nor efficient format. For the future version of the TNA Programme, we would like to move towards a more regular or even an ongoing application cycle where possible, facilitated by a RESILIENCE TNA Online Portal.

This portal is in line with the RESILIENCE Service Strategy, in that it is user-driven, enables easy exchange of information, reduces management overhead costs, and makes it easier for TNA Fellows and Hosts to communicate with each other. It will be a dedicated platform on the RESILIENCE marketplace, to be used by RESILIENCE members, TNA Hosts, and TNA Fellows. The overall aim is to create a single access-point for all of the services and information related to RESILIENCE TNA: the TNA Hosts and their collections, automated TNA Fellow application procedures, communicate funding opportunities, and highlighting TNA success stories. The first two years of the preparatory phase were dedicated to setting up the prototype TNA Programme, and to create and grow the initial TNA Hosting Network. That work revealed the need for a dedicated TNA Portal. However, no effort or resources were foreseen at this stage of the project for prototyping or developing such a portal. This will take place in the future, but will very likely not be possible until 2030, which is when the Financial Sustainability Plan foresees the inclusion of a fulltime

³³ This was launched in August 2024 for the first time. See <https://www.resilience-ri.eu/evaluation-form-tna-host/> for the questionnaire.

³⁴ The RESILIENCE TNA impact assessment methodology is currently being developed in cooperation with WP5 and will be presented by WP5 in: RESILIENCE D5.1 Impact Analysis.

software developer within RESILIENCE. For now, we foresee that the TNA Portal will have three specific goals in addition to the overall aims highlighted above:

1. To automate the RESILIENCE effort as possible, reserving partner effort for 1) evaluating and improving processes, 2) implementing new initiatives and 3) networking and collaboration.
2. To make the TNA network more efficient and more easily accessible for TNA Fellows. The portal will allow users to search for RESILIENCE TNA institutes and their specific physical and virtual collections, as well as researchers according to academic discipline, experts, and research topic. It will do this by importing data via a RSS feed from the institution, sourced from publicly available profiles and information.
3. To create a networking and collaboration platform for TNA Hosts: GLAM institutes, archives and libraries, institutes of higher education. In the long run, such a platform can provide an ongoing, sustainable environment which can serve as the starting point for transnational collaboration on the institutional level, with the aim of increasing the success rate of large grant applications, forming a negotiating block for projects involving the for-profit sector, as well as knowledge and staff exchanges.

Apart from more efficient access, the TNA Portal will also automate a number of the TNA procedures, to reduce the human effort needed to run the programme. At minimum these processes will include the TNA Fellow applications and evaluations, initial contact for TNA Hosts, overview of all TNA Hosts, and TNA Host Evaluations. The portal will at minimum include the following features:

1. **List of searchable TNA Hosts.** These should be searchable by institute name, city and country, type of institute (HEI - university, Library, Archive, Museum, other), and available expertise.
2. **TNA Fellow Application Portal.** This section automatizes the application process for TNA Fellows where possible. Applications are automatically forwarded to the relevant TNA Host, RESILIENCE Communications officer, and RESILIENCE TNA programme officer. The TNA Coordinator of the Host will then respond with the results of the application. If positive, they will then take the first steps for planning the TNA visit. The TNA Coordinator communicates the results to the RESILIENCE Programme Officer. Evaluation forms will then be sent by the system, based on the dates of the application. ORCID IDs form part of the application.
3. **TNA Host Application Portal.** There is less room for automatizing here. Potential hosts reach out to RESILIENCE via a contact form embedded in the portal. Each new TNA Host needs to be confirmed by the Peer Review Committee. The creation of the TNA Host webpages will be done by the RESILIENCE Communications Officer.
4. **Evaluations.** Evaluation links will be sent to the TNA Fellow after their research stay via the TNA Portal. These will be summarized and analysed by the Portal into a short report. That report will be supplemented and finalized by the RESILIENCE Programme Officer, and sent to RESILIENCE HQ. The evaluations for the TNA Hosts will be conducted annually, and fully analysed and reported on by the programme officer to RESILIENCE HQ.

Developing the TNA Portal is subject to RESILIENCE entering the implementation phase, and dependent on funding made available to do so. It is too early yet for an estimation of running costs.

4.2 Expanding the TNA Hosting Network

Expansion of the TNA Hosting Network will be an ongoing and carefully curated part of the TNA Programme. The priorities listed below should be kept in mind for the first two years of the programme, after which evaluation and monitoring of the project should dictate future strategies. Throughout however, the network should remain as diverse as possible on the geographic, religious and disciplinary level.

4.2.1 GLAM sector

For galleries and museums, we are in the process of updating our procedures and communication packages. Unlike institutes of higher education, not many museums or art galleries will have experience hosting visiting research fellows, or procedures in place that we can use. Talks with potential G/M hosts will therefore have to be more extensive. The potential here however, is worthwhile: within The study of religion there is a strong movement towards material history, oral history, and even audiovisual history. RESILIENCE would be offering an entirely unique service by including exchanges with museums and galleries in its offer of TNA Hosts. Many of our TNA Hosts will have existing connections and collaborations with national museums which can be leveraged to this end, though here too the expansion will have to be curated carefully to guarantee excellence.

In addition to museums and archives we will also explore the potential of including religious institutes such as monasteries, churches, mosques, and synagogues. A good current example is the Bektashi Headquarters, who are one of the first TNA hosts within this category. However, here it is clear that specific criteria and guidelines need to be developed, as well as relationships cultivated that can mediate between the researcher and the religious institute. This will require careful negotiation and monitoring on the part of RESILIENCE, while at the same time providing access to an entirely unique resource within the study of religion and the humanities.

4.2.2 Geographic Expansion

In line with the communication strategy, the initial focus within Europe will be Eastern Europe and the Balkans. Plans were in place for MENA expansion, but given the current regional instability this has been put on hold for now. Expansion towards Ireland/the UK, Scandinavia, France/Spain, and Central Europe is crucial to maintain European diversity and the sustainability of the programme. These are dependent on the expansion of the RESILIENCE RI in the preparatory phase.

4.2.3 Creating an Active Network

In addition to these concrete expansion strategies, the other emphasis will be on expanding outgoing as well as incoming mobility. The first two calls were chiefly focused on external TNA Fellows applying to visit a TNA Host, with the TNA Host functioning as a passive recipient of applications. This should instead become more of a two-way street, in which TNA Hosts actively present the programme to their scholars as an exchange option. The goal is to achieve an energetic network of incoming and outgoing exchanges for each host.

This, of course, is more difficult to present to external TNA Hosts, due to lack of funding. It will be piloted in this phase by RESILIENCE TNA Host members, who have an in-kind duty towards TNA of 30 person months

per partner. During the implementation phase the aim will be to create an active exchange network, in which each TNA Hosts both receives and sends out TNA Fellows.

4.3 Risks and Mitigations

A number of risks have already been identified at this stage of the project; we also foresee a number of challenges for the upcoming transition phase. The list below is not exhaustive, but gives a good indication of the main point.

4.3.1 Risks concerning the transition to the RESILIENCE Implementation Phase.

- Unfunded TNA during implementation phase.
- Delays in the development of the TNA Portal.
- Delays in the transition from PP to Implementation phase.

In all these cases the in-kind version of the TNA Programme can be continued for a longer period of time to facilitate the transition. Individual TNA Hosts can be contacted for local funding possibilities, which can be included in the TNA benefits for that TNA host. Delays in the development of the portal are easier to mitigate, as the current RESILIENCE TNA website is sufficiently developed to run the current version of the programme.

4.3.2 Risks concerning the TNA Hosting Network

- Challenging to maintain a brand of excellence across such a wide variety (geographical, thematic, size) of institutions, thereby risking a too broad/vague brand of TNA.
 - Mitigation: Develop strategies to recruit suitable hosts.
- Theological and religious studies archives, libraries, and institutions are often quite small and might struggle with fulfilling the minimal duties, both on an institutional level, and on a staff level.
 - Mitigation: While the minimum duties cannot be further reduced, it is possible to conflate personnel roles. We will also investigate the possible role of the national coordinator in such cases, and/or the possibility of collaboration between local institutes.
- While smaller institutions counterbalance the lack of dedicated funds with the visibility gained by being part of RESILIENCE, bigger institutions, which are already well known, ask for unique benefits in comparison to other programmes and/or their everyday activities.
 - The benefits for larger institutions relate more to access to the RI as a whole, which in the current phase is still in development.

4.3.3 Risks concerning the individual TNA stays:

- The material for the TNA user is not available in facility/library.
 - This is something that the TNA Host Coordinator should flag upon receiving the application. In that case the TNA applicant will be informed of this and if possible recommended to a different TNA Host that does possess the required expertise.
- Experts not available at the time TNA user is at the facility
 - This should be mitigated by the TNA Host Coordinator by making sure the TNA Fellow has provided more than one suggestion for an expert.
- Lack of TNA proposals from qualified applicants.

- Should this remain consistent the National Node Coordinator will plan a meeting to determine a strategy for mitigating this, e.g. more communication and PR in their specific expertise.
- The planned TNA budget is not sufficient for the TNA user due to unforeseen price increases.
 - This will have to be mitigated via shorter research stays and/or more digital and virtual research stays. If there is an option to increase the budget that is the preferred solution.
- A host institution withdraws from the RESILIENCE TNA programme to which TNA fellows are still to join.
 - While this is obviously not encouraged, it has happened once during the PP phase, for reasons outside of the TNA Host's control. The immediate solution is to try to arrange for these fellows to stay at the institution for the remaining time and/or to find an alternative host institution.
- A pandemic/disaster/war and other events prevent physical access.
 - In this case we will explore the options of virtual and digital access, and focus on finding alternative hosts not located in the affected region.

5. Communication and Impact

This section will address communication strategies and how the impact of the TNA Programme will be measured from the implementation phase onward. Both of these have been, or will be developed in close collaboration with WP4 (Communication and Dissemination) and WP5 (Impact).

5.1 Communication Strategy Frame for TNA

It is recommended that the "Communication Strategy Frame for the RESILIENCE TNA Programme", which was developed in the PP by WP4 in cooperation with WP2, be continuously followed up for an agile development of the communication strategy.³⁵ The strategy aims to reach the target groups relevant to RESILIENCE, including potential TNA fellows, potential TNA hosts and the flow of information to other target groups. The framework for the implementation phase must be adapted to the changed conditions (funding opportunities, modified scope, etc.).

5.2 Guide for the TNA Communication Workflow

To ensure the communication and dissemination of each RESILIENCE TNA scholarship, the WP4 CDE developed a (currently confidential) TNA Communication Workflow guide, which describes the specific measures to be taken. This guide can be used as a basis for the communication workflow in the next phase. Results are news items on the RESILIENCE website and/or on the RESILIENCE social media channels.

5.3 Action Plan for Social Media Content

A social media strategy should be included in the TNA communication strategy framework. It is recommended to operate with an Action Plan that acts as a calendar for all social media content and ensures that all relevant planned actions are shared on social media. In the context of TNA, this includes news about the TNA research stays, the calls, news about TNA hosts, webinars for TNA fellows or hosts,

³⁵ RESILIENCE_WP4_D4.2_CDEP, chap. 3.3, available from December 2024 via <https://www.resilience-ri.eu/deliverables/>. See also Annex 7.9.

results of these various activities, publications due to RESILIENCE TNA and other topics of interest in this regard.³⁶

5.4 Measuring Impact

The RESILIENCE work package on impact is still in the process of developing a strategy and management plan for measuring impact of the future RI. As one of the few active services, they prioritized the creation of an impact plan for TNA. This section summarizes the key aspects of this plan, though it should be noted that this is still a work in progress.

Within TNA, they have identified three levels of data that need to be taken into account: output data, outcome data, and impact data. Output data consists of measurable results. For TNA this includes the number of TNA Hosts and Fellows and their demographics (institutional affiliation, geographic location, level of education), as well as the diversity of participants and their evaluation of TNA activities. Outcome data provides insight on the benefits experienced by Fellows as well as Hosts in the TNA programme, such as acquired knowledge and skills, scientific publications, international research collaborations, and increase in access of collections. Finally, impact data captures the long-term effects of the programme, providing insights on changes in the organizational capacity and societal resilience. This also includes the impact on underrepresented groups and regions, economic impact via innovation, and solutions to global challenges. The work package on impact is working out indicators and approaches for measuring this within the context of the RI as a whole, as well as the role of TNA within it.

5.5 Open science & FAIR Principle

In line with the RESILIENCE Service Strategy, TNA intends to “[...] safeguard our community’s research output should be both FAIR and sustainable”. In the case of TNA, we incorporate FAIR as a guiding principle in its service management, and focus on Open Science and Open Access as guiding principles within the context of the TNA Programme.³⁷ The most concrete example for the current stage of the programme of this is that we ask that all scientific output that relates to the TNA Visit of a TNA Fellow be published Open Access, *where this is feasible*. Due to the individual or institutional costs associated with open access publication this is not something we wish to enforce, but we will encourage it where possible.

6. Conclusion

The RESILIENCE TNA Programme forms a crucial part of the current and future RESILIENCE ecosystem. It ensures physical access to sources and collections, and helps increase the networking currency of both individual TNA Fellows and the TNA Hosting Network. The relatively high number of TNA Fellows during the preparatory phase shows that there is a need for such a service, especially for early and mid-career scholars. Funding the programme will help facilitate access for those scholars who are currently not able to fund their own research stay, as well as contribute to increasing equality of access across Europe.

The current version of the management plan is a beta deliverable, and therefore still in development. In the next period we will focus on developing and finalizing these sections. These include:

³⁶ Cf. as an example D4.2, Attachment 2: Action Plan M13-M27, available from December 2024 via <https://www.resilience-ri.eu/deliverables/>.

³⁷ Service Strategy Plan, p. 9.

1. Developing an updated agreement between RESILIENCE and the TNA Host that includes the financial and legal obligations required for a funded programme. This will be done in close collaboration with ITSERR due to their current experience with running a (limited) funded agreement, and to ensure that both individual and team mobility is covered in the agreement template.
2. Developing strategies to ease the transition between the PP phase and the implementation phase, including clear and detailed plans for potential delays. This will become more clear as the PP progresses, and will be developed based on the deliverables and insights from WP1.
3. Finalizing the impact measurement strategy for the TNA Programme, in collaboration with WP5. We have received a first draft of this strategy, and have been able to include a short summary in this version.
4. Developing strategies for integrating the future TNA Programme within the RESILIENCE Ecosystem of Service, with special attention for WU Training. As the service strategy and service catalogue are taking shape this will become clearer. As part of this we also work on further integrating and deepening the current TNA Hosting Network.
5. Fine-tuning existing workflows and procedures, based on current results and experiences. This includes developing a rubric describing the TNA Fellow criteria of acceptance.

7. Annexes

ID	Title
1.	MOU TNA Host 2024-2026 Template
2.	Host information package
3.	Template Recommendation Report New TNA Host
4.	TNA Host Evaluation Form
5.	TNA Fellow Evaluation Form
6.	TNA Letter of Invitation Template
7.	TNA Certificates for Fellows
8.	TNA Fellow Selection Criteria Chart for TNA Hosts
9.	Communication Strategy Frame TNA
10.	TNA Fellow Terms and Conditions
11.	TNA Fellow Online Application (<i>downloaded online form</i>)

7.1 TNA Host Memorandum of Understanding 2024–2026

Preamble

This Memorandum of Understanding (MOU) is entered into by and between:

- (A) European Research Infrastructure on Religious Studies (hereafter RESILIENCE).
- (B) TNA HOST

The RESILIENCE Transnational Access Programme (TNA) offers physical and virtual access to an expanding network of European institutions and libraries. Its aim is to facilitate and foster easy access to sources, resources, expertise and services for researchers in Religious Studies in all their synchronic and diachronic variety, as well as promoting and disseminating collections, institutions, and archives. Considering the desire of the TNA HOST to become a RESILIENCE TNA host, this Memorandum of Understanding lists the mutual roles and responsibilities of each party in taking part to the TNA Programme and is intended to promote and ensure the excellence of the RESILIENCE TNA Fellowship Programme.

Roles and Responsibilities

Commitments of TNA HOST: To ensure excellence RESILIENCE asks hosts to provide a minimum of duties, which can be summarised as follows:

1. Appoint a RESILIENCE TNA coordinator and a TNA Contact Person. These roles may be performed by one person, if preferred:

TNA Coordinator	TNA Contact Person
Reviews Applications	Point of Contact for TNA Scholar
Provides a letter of invitation	Responsible for practical and administrative duties
Ensures a smooth operation within university bureaucracy	Keeps RESILIENCE TNA Coordinator? informed of progress

2. Please list below the name and contact details of the TNA Coordinator and TNA Contact Person:

TNA Coordinator:

TNA Contact Person (if different to Coordinator):

3. Agree to a minimum number of TNA recipients per academic year: [x].
4. Review and accept TNA applications for your institution, using the TNA Review Criteria.
5. Ensure the provision of a comfortable workspace for each TNA recipient
6. Match TNA recipients with at minimum one onsite scholar or expert.

7. Report to RESILIENCE on the performance of the TNA program and help to develop and improve the TNA program and its procedures.
8. Participate in promoting RESILIENCE TNA, TNA Scholars, and TNA research results, through internal and external communication channels.
9. Permit RESILIENCE to publish a description of your physical and digital collections on your TNA Host webpage as a part of the RESILIENCE website.
10. [additional specific services offered by TNA Host]
11. [additional specific services offered by TNA Host]

Commitments of RESILIENCE

12. RESILIENCE offers access to the RESILIENCE PR and communication channels for recognition and dissemination of the TNA HOST unique collections
13. RESILIENCE offers access to a top-level network of researchers and institutions related to religious studies.
14. RESILIENCE offers access to a growing set of services and tools tailored to research within your fields of expertise.
15. RESILIENCE is responsible for organising and disseminating each TNA Call for Fellowships.
16. RESILIENCE undertakes to grow the TNA Host network.
17. RESILIENCE monitors the quality of the TNA programme as a whole via targeted evaluation processes.
18. RESILIENCE is responsible for keeping all TNA Hosts up to date on all relevant news and updates concerning the programme and the life of the RI in general.

Participating in this Programme also provides TNA HOST with the following additional benefits:

19. Join a unique European research infrastructure for religious studies.
20. Attract and boost interaction with TNA HOST physical and virtual collections by top-level researchers.
21. Foster peer-reviewed publications specific to TNA HOST collections.
22. Access a network of high-ranking institutions with unique and valuable collections related to religious studies.
23. Participate in an international exchange network of researchers, scholars, archivists, librarians, stakeholders, and policy makers.

RESILIENCE understands that not all institutions can provide the same resources. Therefore, the RI has outlined the minimum commitment which will ensure excellence and hospitality. If there are any additional services available at the TNA HOST have not been included in this MoU, but become available over time, agrees to communicate about them with RESILIENCE in due time.

Final Statement

With this MoU, the TNA HOST joins the RESILIENCE TNA Programme as a TNA host for the duration of the next two academic years: 01-06-2024 – 31-05-2026). After that date the MOU is subject to renegotiation. Any and all contributions of all parties are in-kind. No financial compensation is offered by or to either party for the duration of this MOU.

This Memorandum of Understanding is the complete agreement between RESILIENCE and the TNA HOST and may be amended only by written agreement signed by each of the parties involved. Signatories must be officially authorised to sign on behalf of the parties and include title and party's name.

Signed,

[date, location]

[Name]

[Role at institution:]

[date, location]

[Name]

RESILIENCE TNA Coordinator 2022-2026

7.2 TNA Host Information Package

Timeline [Academic Year]

Call for Application:	
Deadline reviews for TNA hosts:	
Notification of Acceptance to TNA users:	
TNA visits 2023:	
TNA visits 2024:	

Appoint a TNA contact person

In addition to the overall coordination within your institution, part of being a TNA host is going to include quite a lot of communication and making practical arrangements. This is especially the case before and during the TNA visit: arranging airport pick-ups (if included in your offer), making sure material is readied, arranging meet and greets, ensuring deadlines are met, etc.

It could be the case that for some of you that it's easier to appoint a separate person who can be responsible for the day to day follow-up of TNA arrangements/practicalities.

Overview of responsibilities:

TNA Coordinator	TNA Contact Person
Reviews Applications	Point of Contact for TNA Scholar
Provides a letter of invitation	Responsible for practical and administrative duties
Ensures a smooth operation within university bureaucracy	Keeps RESILIENCE TNA informed of progress

Insurance

Please check what the insurance policies are at your institution regarding Visiting Scholars. If the TNA visit is not included in your standard policies, **please inform the TNA scholar!** They might then need to buy travel insurance.

TNA Visit: Full Script

One month after the application deadline, the TNA hosts have decided which applicants are accepted and which are rejected. Then the local TNA Coordinator or Contact informs the applicants.

Tip sheet

The tip sheet is part of the initial welcome. It's a pre-written email or document which contains all the general information your TNA scholar needs to know. This does not yet concern specific arrangements and requests, but it does contain more detail than your TNA Host webpages. Those are intended as a general overview, whereas with this tip sheet we would like to create a more personal sense of welcome. Try to include as many details as possible, preferably with using **English language links**: addresses, opening times, ticket/entry costs, links to events, etc.

A small tip: when including links, make sure these are publicly available links, and not part of your institutional intranet requiring specific access!

In the Template TNA Host Tip Sheet are some suggestions, but please note that this is not an exhaustive list! I'm sure that many of you have enough experiences both hosting Visiting Scholars and traveling as Visiting Scholars to add to this list. In addition to this, you yourself know your institution, city, and country best. For example, the siesta times in Spain can make mid-afternoon appointments difficult – this is something that could be useful to know for a TNA user, but is only relevant for Spain. **A useful place for finding such tips are emails and information packages from congresses hosted at your institution. See also the KU Leuven template.**

The most important message is that **TNA is a Service** – anything a host can do to make a visit more efficient, hospitable, and friendly, is worth considering!

Template Tip Sheet

1. Welcoming message

[About 50-100 words]

2. Travel and accommodation tips
 - a. Traveling to and from institution
 - b. Address of your accommodation (if included)
3. Recommended accommodation:
 - a. Links to hotels, AirBnB's
 - b. (Public) Transportation
 - c. Bus/Bike/Uber/other options
4. Preparing the research activities
 - a. Library/Collection: [Opening Hours](#) / [Setting up an Account](#) / [Limo](#) catalogue / [printing, scanning, and copying](#)
 - b. Library/Collection: [Opening hours](#) / [Visiting the collections](#) (procedures)
 - c. Please see [...] for any events taking place during your visit
 - d. [Other institutions](#)
5. Leisure suggestions
 - a. Parks and Gardens
 - b. Museums
 - c. (Academic) Book Shops

d. Restaurants / cafés

Check procedures for any congresses or conferences that have taken place at your institution - very often these also contain useful information and tips for visiting scholars.

7.3 TNA Host Recommendation Report Template

General information:

RESILIENCE Contact Person: [Full Name, Institutional affiliation]

Name TNA Host Institution: [Full name and acronym]

Date of Application: [dd-mm-yy]

Weblink institute:

Type of institute: [Archive/Library/Institute of Higher Education/Art Gallery/Museum/other]

Nationality:

Main language(s) spoken at institute:

Admissions Criteria TNA Hosts: please indicate yes or no for each criterium.

1. Aware of the financial commitment required to fulfill minimum duties of a TNA host. **(yes/no)**
2. Dean/Director of the institution has signed (or is willing to sign) the memorandum of understanding **(yes/no)**
3. Has appointed a TNA Coordinator and TNA Contact Person (can be one person) **(yes/no)**
4. Holds one or more academic collections relevant to the field of religious studies **(yes/no)**
5. Host institution has a number of in-house experts/senior scholars affiliated with disciplines related to religious studies and/or experts on the collections in their holdings **(yes/no)**
6. Host institution is located within Horizon Europe list of European nations **(yes/no)**
7. Host institution is GDPR compliant and operates according to OA and FAIR principles **(yes/no)**
8. Host institution has an online presence (newsletters, social media, website) which can be utilized for RESILIENCE communication and PR **(yes/no)**
9. Host institution aims to provide a safe space to excellent researchers regardless of gender, age, nationality or impairments **(yes/no)**

Minimum Duties TNA Host

The TNA Host has been informed of, and has indicated a commitment towards the minimum duties listed below required to host a TNA scholar:

10. Agree to a minimum number of TNA recipients per academic year. **(Yes/no. [number])**
11. Review and accept TNA applications for your institution, using the TNA Review Criteria. **(yes/no)**
12. Ensure the provision of a comfortable workspace for each TNA recipient. **(yes/no)**
13. Match TNA recipients with at minimum one onsite scholar/expert. **(yes/no)**
14. Report to RESILIENCE on the performance of the TNA program and help to develop and improve the TNA program and its procedures. **(yes/no)**
15. Participate in promoting RESILIENCE TNA, TNA Scholars, and TNA research results, through internal and external communication channels. **(yes/no)**

16. Permit RESILIENCE to publish a description of your physical and digital collections on your TNA Host webpage as a part of the RESILIENCE website. **(yes/no)**

Additional Services

The TNA Host has these additional services at their disposal, which they have indicated can be utilized by potential TNA Scholars:

17. [...]

18. [...]

Recommendation RESILIENCE Contact Person

Please indicate in a few lines your official recommendation to the TNA Host Evaluation Working Group, and explain why.

[...]

7.4 TNA Host Evaluation Form

The TNA Host Evaluation form was developed in 2024. It can be accessed online here: [TNA Host Evaluation Form](#)

7.5 TNA Fellow Evaluation Form

The TNA Fellow Evaluation Form was developed in 2022. It can be accessed online here: [TNA Fellow Evaluation Form](#)

7.6 TNA Letter of Invitation Template

Invitation for a RESILIENCE TNA Research Fellowship

[date], [location]

To whom it may concern

TNA Fellow: [Title] [Name] [Institute of origin]

TNA Host: [name centre/archive if relevant], [name TNA Host]

This is to certify that [Name TNA Scholar] has been awarded a fellowship to pursue academic research at the [name TNA Host], within the frame of the EU ESFRI research infrastructure RESILIENCE, which offers Transnational Access to Special Collections and Archival Documents within the field of religious studies. [Name] has specified a research program which [short description research]. He/She is therefore warmly invited to spend [length of stay] at [TNA Host] to conduct research in their libraries and collections, as well as meet experts. His/Her stay in [TNA Host] is planned from **[Exact Dates Research Stay]**. The RESILIENCE TNA fellowship program provides free access to the institution and the required collections, a place to work, as well as ensuring contact with relevant experts during the visit.

TNA coordinator and point of contact at [TNA Host]

[Name TNA Coordinator], [email TNA Coordinator]

About RESILIENCE

RESILIENCE is a unique, interdisciplinary and invigorating research infrastructure for Religious Studies, building a high-performance platform, supplying evolving tools and big data to scholars from all the scientific disciplines crossing religions in their diachronical and synchronical variety.

The ESFRI Forum included RESILIENCE in its 2021 Roadmap, placing it in the strategic framework for Research Infrastructures in the European Research Area. RESILIENCE Preparatory Phase Project (2022-2026) is funded by the European Union under Grant Agreement No 101079792.

Contact: tna_scholar@resilience-ri.eu

7.7 TNA Certificates for Fellows

CERTIFICATE OF FELLOWSHIP for Transnational Access

This is to certify that

was awarded a RESILIENCE TNA Fellowship

at

from to

to conduct research on the research project:

The fellowship offered access to sources, documents, manuscripts, rare books, resources, instruments, files and databases available through the TNA Host, combined with direct contact with experts in the field of research.

Description of work:

The workload amounted to about hours within this period.

Date:

Signature:

Name:

CERTIFICATE

7.8 TNA Fellow Selection Criteria Chart for TNA Hosts

Evaluation of Applications for RESILIENCE Transnational Access

Evaluator	
Evaluators Institution	

Main Selection and Ranking Criteria (points: 0-10) -> use drop-down menu	
1	Research quality of the proposal.
2	Originality of the research activity.
3	User demonstrates a record of academic excellence.
4	The research project is expected to lead to academic output.
5	The project is relevant to RESILIENCE.

Extra Criteria (Yes/No) -> use drop-down menu	
A	The project has a woman group leader or principal investigator, or the gender balance within the group members is fulfilled, or it includes a specific focus on gender issues.
B	The project is led by a young scholar (Bachelor, Master, PhD) who aims to significantly improve his training in humanities and particularly in Religious Studies.
C	The project is proposed by a user who belongs to a country with limited or no access to (re) sources in Religious Studies.
D	The project requires a strong integration between the access to special collections and the use of digital tools.
E	The project is interdisciplinary in nature, or demonstrates a need for intersectoral collaboration.

Applicant (surname, first name)	Main Criteria					Extra Criteria (Yes/No)					Results		Acceptance (Yes/No)	Comments
	1	2	3	4	5	A	B	C	D	E	Results 1	Results 2	"Yes" applicable >25p.	
											0	0		
											0	0		
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7.9 Communication Strategy Frame TNA

7.10 TNA Fellow Terms and Conditions

The RESILIENCE Transnational Access Programme offers physical and virtual access to an expanding network of European institutions and libraries. Its aim is to facilitate and foster easy access to sources, resources, expertise and services for researchers in Religious Studies in all their synchronic and diachronic variety, as well as promoting and disseminating collections, institutions, and archives. This document lists the mutual roles and responsibilities of each party in taking part in the TNA Programme and is intended to promote and ensure the excellence of the RESILIENCE TNA Fellowship Programme.

Duties of your TNA Host

1. **Workspace:** Ensure the provision of a comfortable workspace for each TNA recipient
2. **Expert:** Match TNA recipients with, at minimum, one onsite scholar or expert.
3. **Access:** Access to the TNA Host's physical and virtual collections
4. **Facilitating the visit:** Contact with a member of the TNA Host institution to help organize and facilitate the visit.

Criteria of Your TNA Stay

5. **TNA Fellowship Requirements:** While a TNA Fellowship does not include a report of your activities, there are three requirements for TNA Fellows:
 1. **Evaluating your stay:** Upon completing your visit you will receive an evaluation form from RESILIENCE TNA. Please complete this as soon as possible to help us improve the programme for future TNA Fellows.
 2. **Communication:** Send us a short quote, picture, or paragraph describing a key insight, your experiences, or summarizing your research. These will be used for the TNA Communication channels.
 3. **Scientific Output:** Please send us any scientific output that you were able to complete as a result of your TNA stay. This can be an academic article, a conference presentation, or any kind of scientific communication relevant to your stay and expertise.
6. **Transnational research stay:** your TNA visit should not take place in the same country as your official nationality. In case of multiple nationalities, your visit should take place outside of the country you currently reside in.
7. **Dates of your research stay:** Your TNA visit should be planned starting from one month after you have received the results of your TNA application, and can be planned within one calendar year of that date.
8. **Length of your research stay:** TNA Visits usually last between one week and two weeks. For longer visits, please contact your TNA Coordinator.
9. **Postponing or canceling your research stay:** Your TNA visit can be postponed once. Please inform your TNA Coordinator, as well as TNA RESILIENCE of your intention to postpone, as well as the dates of your visit. Should you find yourself needing to cancel your TNA visit altogether, please inform both your TNA Coordinator and TNA RESILIENCE as soon as possible, and up to two weeks before the start of your visit. Please include a reason for your cancellation.

7.11 TNA Fellow Online Application (downloaded online form)